

**ABDULLA QAHHOR VA EDGAR ALLAN PO HIKOYALARIDA
QO‘RQINCHLILIK TASVIRIDAGI UYG‘UNLIKLAR
(Abdulla Qahhornig “Dahshat” va Edgar Allan Poning “Yurak” hikoyalari
asosida)**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola ikki hikoyanavislar Abdulla Qahhor va Edgar Alan Po ijodi va ularning “Dahshat” va “Yurak” hikoyalarida qo‘rqinchlilik tasvirining ifodalanishidagi o‘hshashliklarni yoritadi. Asar syujeti va qahramonlarining farqli jihatlarini qiyoslaydi.

Kalit so‘zlar: romantist, Ego-vigil va Superego-yomon, yoritish, folklor, dodhoh.

**COMPATIBILITIES OF FEAR IN THE STORIES OF ABDULLA KAHHOR
AND EDGAR ALLAN POE**

**(Based on the stories “Horror” by Abdullah Kahhor and “The tale-heart” by
Edgar Alan Poe)**

Annotation: This article highlights the work of two storytellers, Abdullah Kahhor and Edgar Alan Paul, and the similarities in the depiction of horror in their stories “Horror” and “The tale-heart”. The work also compares the different aspects of the plot and the central characters.

Key words: romanticist, Ego-vigil and Superego-evil, illumination, folklore, dodhoh

There are fearful stories in every culture, which wake strange feelings in booklovers. They take a great deal of talent on the part of a writer to fit such a theme into a single story and bring it to the level of a masterpiece. The American romanticist Edgar Allan Poe's story "The tale-tell heart" and the great Uzbek storyteller Abdullah Kahhor's literary work "Horror" are real examples of this theme. These stories have several similarities as well as differences on the author's descriptions.

Both writers Edgar Allan Pole, an American poet, writer and representative of Romanticism, and Uzbek novelist Abdulla Kahhor are famous for their short stories. Edgar Allan Poe was one of the first practitioners of short story writing in his country

and was considered the inventor of the detective and science fiction genres. Magdalen Wing, a researcher of Poe’s works, states that the writer often uses Ego-vigil and Superego-evil in his works. She defines the term Ego-Evil for people who are as self-loved and Superego-Evil for fanatical devotion. These are the essentials of Poe’s stories as the narrator kills an innocent old man for getting rid of evil eye and became a murderer soon. The linguist argues that although Poe’s heroes know the difference between right and wrong, they do not care about their sins. However, Poe’s characters are not remained unattended for long due to the inquisitive gaze of others and they admit their guilts soon. Nevertheless, the heroes’ confessions often do not guide to their deliverance or to show their guilt. [7,1]

Abdulla Kahhor is a master of depiction of tragic stories in Uzbek literature of the twentieth century. His stories amaze with their sincerity and persuasive power. Many of the writer's stories are based on real life events that the writer practiced in his and acquaintances life. After all, this is the secret of the vitality and persuasive power of the writer’s stories. The author's unique artistic perception of the events of his life, his original and diverse discovery of them, also gave a special charm to the stories. [1,1]

The stories “The tell-tale heart” and “Dahshat” have many similarities with each other. Both works begin with fearful descriptions. The events begin in dark night and express tough situations. The core similarity in these works is the main characters’ desire to escape from difficult surroundings.

The title of Poe’s story tells the reader that a secret must be kept secret. The main idea of “The tell-tale heart” is when a man makes a crime, he cannot go far from the murdering place and escape from his feelings as well. The story is told by a nameless narrator who starts his speech strangely, with negative illuminations that he is not mad but wants to speak about his murdering an old man because of his hatred towards a man’s blue eyes.

“True, I'm nervous. Very, very dreadfully nervous. But why would you say that I'm mad? See how calmly, how precisely I can tell the story to you. Listen. It starts with the old man. And old man in an old house. A good man, I suppose. He didn't harm me, I didn't want his gold, if gold there was. Then what was it? I think... I think it was... his eye. Yes, that eye, the eye. That. His eye staring. Milky white film. The eye, everywhere, in everything! Of course, I had to get rid of the eye.”[4,1]

Indeed, the narrator is a young man who dislikes his neighbor’s pale eyes and wants to escape from them by killing that man. Though the narrator emphasizes the careful calculation of the murder, the attempted perfect crime, the dismemberment of the body in the bathroom, and the hiding under the floorboards, it is understood from the context that he is mentally ill. Eventually, as a result of the narrator’s actions, he hears a beating sound, and the narrator interprets this as a dead man’s heart beating.

Abdullah Kahhor used folklore to create the plot of "Horror". The Muslim cemetery is one of the most terrifying places due to ancient religious legends. Therefore, it is a sign of courage for men to finish something at the cemetery at night or to bring something from the grave. Although a similar story is told in "Horror", Kahhor uses a different approach. First of all, the leading role of the story is an ordinary girl who agrees with her fate and cannot refuse to marry an old man, and she does not possess the character of a heroine. This enhances the emotional and dramatic power of the event. The circumstances of the incident will also change considerably. Not to pierce the grave with a knife, but to boil water and make tea. If Unsin can accomplish the task, it is agreed that her husband Olimbekdodhoh will divorce and allow her to go home. Though the author gives no information about the nature of the character who agrees with this, it is understood from the context of the story. In “Horror” the writer wants to show the hard lifestyle of Uzbek women and describes that time’s traditions that men could marry several times and young, poor girls were the sacrifices of this tyrant period.

Go ‘riston to ‘g ‘risida dodxo nimalar eshitgan bo ‘lsa, Unsin ham shuni eshitgan, shamol kechasi go ‘riston dodxo xayolida qandoq dahshatli bo ‘lsa, uning xayolida ham shunday dahshatli, lekin shundoq bo ‘lsa ham, tiriklar go ‘ristoni bo ‘lgan bu dargohning dahshati oldida o ‘liklar go ‘ristonining dahshati unga dahshat ko ‘rinmas, bundan tashqari, ertagayoq Ganjiravonga jo ‘nash, ota-onasini, dugonalarini ko ‘rish umidi uning boshiga boshqa hech qanday fikr-xayolni yo ‘latmas edi.[6,2]

The most important component within the Poe’s story is the act of murder. This is most important element of the story because without the murder there would be no story. The next most important factor is the narrator's madness. Without the narrator's madness, there would never have been a murder committed. His madness is evident within the first paragraph of the story, although he is desperate to prove otherwise. In addition to the narrator's madness, is his paranoia or anxiety, which plays a key role in his madness because it heightens his mental illness. The main factor in the Kahhor’s story is the endeavor for freedom. If a girl preferred wealth, she would not strive for freedom. The struggle for liberty motivates him to accomplish the hard work given even on a terrible night.

There are some differences in these novels. Firstly, the main character in “The tell-tale heart” is a young man, the author does not give him a name and in “Horror” a young woman, Unsin. Although Allan Poles’ sheroe is a man he chose an easy way to escape from his problem and kills his neighbor. He could have looked for ways to get rid of the hatred eyes or to move anywhere so as not to face the old man. However, in “Horror” the main heroine does not fear from the difficulties and in order to achieve her liberty and wish she tries bravely. In addition, the endings differ from each other

that in “The tell-tale heart” the narrator tells his guilty himself and prisoned but the young lady dies after a terrible night.

In conclusion, both writers are famous for their short stories and analyzed works are their masterpieces. Through his work, Poe expresses that the human imagination exaggerates what it hears and sees. It is up to the reader to accuse or justify the protagonist as innocent, insane, or murderous. Moreover, Abdullah Kahhor’s story describes that for freedom, man is ready to overcome any difficulty, that wealth cannot give men the happiness they desire, and those ignorant people in life cannot comprehend these thoughts.

References:

1. Қўшжонов Матёқуб, Абдулла Қаҳҳор маҳорати:-Т, Адабиёт ва санъат нашриётиб, 1988.
2. Sanjar Sodiq. Abdulla Qahhor ijodi va adabiytanqid. Toshkent, „Universitet“, 1996.
3. Normatov U. Abdulla Qahhorni anglashmashaqqati. Toshkent. „Universitet“, 1999.
4. May, C. E. (2009). “The Tell-Tale Heart.” Beacham's Guide to Literature for Young Adults. USA: Gale Group, Inc. pp. 112 – 136.
5. Meyers, Jeffrey (1992). Edgar Allan Poe: His Life and Legacy (Paperback ed.). New York: Cooper Square Press. Pp. 12 -1 5.
6. <https://orifto.lib.uz/kutubxona/abdulla-qahhor-dahshat-hikoya/>
7. <https://owlcation.com/humanities/Edgar-Allan-Poes-the-Tell-Tale-Heart-A-Literary-Analysis>.